

Implementation of Lucas wavelet functions for solving fractional differential equations

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Abstract

In this study, the Lucas wavelet technique is presented for the solution of fractional differential equations. According to Lucas wavelet functions, modified operational matrix of integration and pseudo-operational matrix of the derivative, we reduced the proposed equations to a system of algebraic equations. Also, the numerical outcomes compare with the results of the other methods in the last section. Illustrative examples demonstrate the validity and applicability of the computational technique.

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1 Introduction

Fractional differential equations have appeared in the modeling of many phenomena in real life, such as electromagnetism [1], fluid-dynamic models [2], and etc. Due to the useful properties of wavelet methods, many researchers have studied in this field (see [3, 4, 5] and references therein).

2 Requirement concepts

2.1 Lucas wavelet functions

The Lucas wavelet functions are defined over the interval $[0, 1)$ as follows [5, 6]:

$$\Psi_{nm}(t) = \begin{cases} 2^{\frac{K-1}{2}} \mathcal{L}_m(2^{K-1}t - n + 1), & \frac{n-1}{2^{K-1}} \leq t < \frac{n}{2^{K-1}}, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M, \quad n = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{K-1}. \quad (2.1)$$

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where

$$\mathfrak{L}_m(2^{K-1}t - n + 1) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\int_0^1 L_m^2(x) dx}} L_m(2^{K-1}t - n + 1),$$

and $L_m(x)$ denotes the Lucas polynomials [5, 6]

$$L_0(x) = 2, \quad L_m(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{m}{2} \rfloor} \frac{m}{m-k} \binom{m-k}{k} x^{m-2k}, \quad m > 0. \quad (2.2)$$

2.2 Modified operational matrix of integration

For achieving the aim of this paper, we compute the modified operational matrix of integration (MOMI). Hence, according to the Lucas wavelet functions and their properties, we get [5]

$$\int_0^t \Psi(\xi) d\xi = \Theta \Psi(t) + \Lambda(t). \quad (2.3)$$

where Θ and $\Lambda(t)$ are MOMI and complement vector, respectively. It should be noted that each component of the matrix is obtained as follows[5]:

$$\int_0^t \Psi_{nm}(\xi) d\xi \simeq \begin{cases} 0, & t < \frac{n-1}{2^{K-1}}, \\ \sum_{s=1}^{2^{K-1}} \sum_{i=0}^M \theta_{si}^{nm} \Psi_{si}(t), & \frac{n-1}{2^{K-1}} \leq t < \frac{n}{2^{K-1}}, \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1, \\ \sum_{s=1}^{2^{K-1}} \sum_{i=0}^M \theta_{si}^{nM} \Psi_{si}(t) + \lambda_M^n, & \frac{n-1}{2^{K-1}} \leq t < \frac{n}{2^{K-1}}, \quad m = M, \\ \sum_{s=1}^{2^{K-1}} \theta_{s0}^{nM} \Psi_{s0}(t), & t \geq \frac{n}{2^{K-1}}. \end{cases} \quad (2.4)$$

2.3 Pseudo-operational matrix of derivative

To compute the fractional derivative of unknown function in the problem, we obtain the pseudo-operational matrix of derivative as follows [5]:

$$D^\nu \Psi(t) = t^{q-\nu} \Upsilon \Psi(t), \quad (2.5)$$

where Υ is called the pseudo-operational matrix of derivative.

3 Numerical technique

This section discusses the numerical approach for solving the following equation:

$$\begin{cases} D^\nu u(t) = F(t, u(t), u'(t), u''(t), D^\gamma u(t)), & 0 < \nu \leq 1, \quad 1 < \gamma \leq 2, \\ u(0) = a_0, \quad u'(0) = a_1. \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

To get the approximate solution, we assume

$$u''(t) = A^T \Psi(t). \quad (3.2)$$

Then, by repeated integrations, we obtain:

$$u'(t) = A^T (\Theta \Psi(t) + \Lambda(t)) + a_1, \quad (3.3)$$

and

$$u(t) = A^T \left(\Theta^2 \Psi(t) + \Theta \Lambda(t) + \int_0^t \Lambda(\xi) d\xi \right) + a_1 t + a_0. \quad (3.4)$$

Furthermore, from the pseudo-operational matrix of derivative, we get

$$D^\nu u(t) = A^T \left(t^{q-\nu} \Theta^2 \Upsilon + \Theta D^\nu \Lambda(t) + D^\nu \left[\int_0^t \Lambda(\xi) d\xi \right] \right) + \frac{\Gamma(2)a_1}{\Gamma(2-\nu)} t^{1-\nu}. \quad (3.5)$$

By substituting Eqs. (3.2)-(3.5) to (3.1) and using Newton-Cotes nodes, we get the system of algebraic equations.

4 Illustrative examples

In this section, we compare the results with Chebyshev wavelets [7, 8] and fractional-order Bessel functions [9], which demonstrate that using the pseudo-operational matrix of the derivative and modified operational matrix of integration affect directly the accuracy of the method.

Example 4.1. Consider the following nonlinear multi-fractional differential equation [7, 8]

$$D^\nu u(t) + D^\gamma u(t) + u^2(t) = (t^2 - t)^2 + \frac{2t^{2-\nu}}{\Gamma(3-\nu)} + \frac{2t^{2-\gamma}}{\Gamma(3-\gamma)} - \frac{t^{1-\gamma}}{\Gamma(2-\gamma)}, \quad 1 < \nu \leq 2, \quad 0 < \gamma \leq 1,$$

subject to $u(0) = 0$, $u'(0) = -1$. The exact solution of this example is $u(t) = t^2 - t$. The results of this problem are illustrated in Table 1 and Figure 1. Table 1 shows the superiority of the method in comparison to Chebyshev wavelets [7, 8].

Example 4.2. Consider the following nonlinear fractional differential equation [9]

$$D^\nu u(t) = -u^2(t) + 1, \quad 0 < \nu \leq 1,$$

subject to $u(0) = 0$. The exact solution of this example for $\nu = 1$, is $u(t) = \frac{\exp(2t)-1}{\exp(2t)+1}$. In Table 2, we compare the results with fractional-order Bessel functions [9], which shows that this method is more accurate than the method in [9]. Figure 2 illustrates that, as approach ν to 1, the approximate solutions converge to the exact solution.

Table 1: Comparison of absolute error obtained by the present method with Refs. [7, 8] for $\nu = 2, \gamma = 0.5$ of Example 6.1.

t	Present method		Ref. [7]	Ref. [8]
	$M = 2, K = 1$	$M = 2, K = 2$	$M = 3, k = 3$	$M = 3, k = 3$
0.1	3.1311×10^{-16}	4.3964×10^{-17}	1.4411×10^{-4}	9.2677×10^{-7}
0.2	1.2468×10^{-16}	1.7133×10^{-16}	1.4007×10^{-4}	3.6193×10^{-6}
0.3	2.7930×10^{-16}	3.7803×10^{-16}	1.3459×10^{-4}	6.3739×10^{-6}
0.4	4.9431×10^{-16}	6.6363×10^{-16}	1.2835×10^{-4}	9.1427×10^{-6}
0.5	7.6888×10^{-16}	1.0313×10^{-15}	1.2241×10^{-4}	1.2129×10^{-5}
0.6	1.1022×10^{-15}	1.4215×10^{-15}	1.1491×10^{-4}	1.4512×10^{-5}
0.7	1.4934×10^{-15}	1.7723×10^{-15}	1.0803×10^{-4}	1.7072×10^{-5}
0.8	1.9416×10^{-15}	2.0844×10^{-15}	1.0114×10^{-4}	1.9533×10^{-5}
0.8	2.4462×10^{-15}	2.5886×10^{-15}	9.4240×10^{-5}	2.1888×10^{-5}

Figure 1: The absolute error for $M = 2$ (left) $M = 3$ (right) with $K = 2, \nu = 2, \gamma = 0.8$ of Example 6.1.

Table 2: Errors for various choices of M with $K = 1$ and $\nu = 1$ of Example 6.2.

	Present method		
	$M = 4$	$M = 6$	$M = 8$
L_2 -error	4.2802×10^{-4}	7.4311×10^{-6}	1.2909×10^{-7}
L_∞ -error	3.2158×10^{-4}	3.6721×10^{-6}	9.2888×10^{-8}
	Ref. [9]		
	$M = 4$	$M = 6$	$M = 9$
L_2 -error	6.33×10^{-4}	1.37×10^{-5}	2.69×10^{-7}
L_∞ -error	3.25×10^{-4}	6.80×10^{-6}	1.19×10^{-7}

Figure 2: The absolute error (left) and approximate solution for different values of $\nu = 0.95, 0.9$ with exact solution (right) for $M = 7, K = 2$ of Example 6.2.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we present an efficient numerical algorithm based on Lucas wavelet functions for solving fractional differential equations. Also, we implemented the method for two problems which demonstrates the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed method.

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